

Neutron Activation Analysis of Molybdenum in Copper Ores*

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Molybdenum in copper ores has been determined by neutron activation analysis, 10.0 μg . of Mo can be estimated with an accuracy of 5% and the sensitivity of the method is 0.2 μg . The chemical yield is 50-60% and the time for separation is less than 45 minutes.

Activation analysis of molybdenum involves the irradiation of copper ores with thermal neutrons to produce 66 hours Mo^{99} by (n, γ) reaction on stable Mo^{98} and its separation in radiochemically pure form from large quantities of other activities. The sample of pure Mo^{99} is allowed to age for the growth of Tc^{99m} and then counted on a gamma-ray spectrometer. The 66 hours Mo^{99} can also be produced by secondary reactions

and so the formation of Mo^{99} from U and Ru, if present, should be considered. The procedure for Mo determination was tested by analysing synthetic mixture of composition very similar to that of the copper ore from Bihar.

EXPERIMENTAL

Irradiations were carried out in the Apsara Reactor or C.I.R. of Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, at a thermal neutron flux of $1-2 \times 10^{12}$ n/cm²/sec. 0.1 g. samples of copper ores (300 mesh) were irradiated along with 1-10 μg . of Mo standard in the form of sodium molybdate, each enclosed in a silica tube and kept in close proximity in a polyethylene tube placed in a standard aluminium can. In the experiments employing internal standards, the ore samples and 0.5 ml of sodium molybdate solution containing 1-10 μg of Mo were taken in silica tubes and after proper drying the tubes were sealed. The irradiated copper ores were fused with 1-3 g. of sodium peroxide in the presence of 15 mg of MoO_3 and 15 mg of KReO_4 and the fused mass was leached with 10+5 ml of water. The extract was centrifuged to remove any suspended materials and the strength of the solution was made 4N with respect to NaOH. It was then equilibrated with 10 ml of pyridine saturated with 4N NaOH to remove rhenium (VII). (This step can be omitted if it is not desired to estimate rhenium¹). The aqueous phase was made acidic with conc. HCl, boiled for a minute, and centrifuged. It was treated with 5 ml of 0.1 M sodium salt of EDTA and adjusted to pH 4.5 with ammonium acetate. After adding 5 ml. of 2% alcoholic solution of α -benzoin oxime², the solution was extracted with 20 ml. of CHCl_3 . The organic phase was washed with 10 ml of water and equilibrated with 20 ml. of aqua regia. The aqueous phase was

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1. Symposium on Nuclear and Radiation Chemistry held at Poona from 6th to 9th March, 1967.

2. H. Knowles, *Bur. Stds. J. Research*, 1930, 9, 1.

boiled for 2 min and raised to pH 6.5 with sodium hydroxide and ammonium acetate. Molybdenum was precipitated³ by adding 5 ml of 2% oxine reagent in acetic acid. The precipitate was centrifuged, washed with 10 ml. of water, dried at 125°, transferred to a stainless steel planchet, and weighed. It was then moistened with a drop of cement, dried under infrared lamp, and counted, after allowing molybdenum activity to attain equilibrium with the daughter Tc^{99m} , on a gamma-ray spectrometer provided with a single channel pulse-height analyser. A $1\frac{1}{2} \times 1\frac{1}{2}$ inch NaI (Tl) crystal was used as a detector. The window of the analyser was usually set at 1 volt but in some measurements the samples were counted with 5 volts window and channel setting corresponding to the minimum of the curve under the peak due to 0.147 MeV γ -ray of Mo^{99} . The instrument was stabilised by using a voltage stabiliser. Small changes in energy calibration of the spectrometer were overcome by recording the spectra of standard Co^{57} source just before and after the measurements. Some samples were counted immediately after radiochemical purification on an end-window G.M. counter through 13.5 mg/cm² of aluminium absorber.

A. R. grade MoO_3 in sodium hydroxide solution was used in the preparation of internal and external standards. Irradiated Mo standard was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and the volume was made up to 250 ml. 1 ml of the solution was transferred to a cone containing 10 mg of Mo carrier and the solution was subjected to the procedure described above for the radio-chemical purification of molybdenum. Synthetic mixtures were prepared from pure A.R. quality ferrous sulfate, copper sulfate, silicon dioxide, calcium oxide, potassium perrhenate and sodium molybdate in appropriate amounts. A sample of the synthetic mixture containing all the constituents, except sodium molybdate, was examined for molybdenum by neutron activation method.

Uranium in the copper ore from Bihar was determined by neutron activation method proposed by Smales⁴ and also colorimetrically by potassium ferrocyanide method⁵. Absorbance was measured on a Unicam Colorimeter, Model SP 300, using 1-cm silica cells. The contribution due to Mo^{99} from the reaction $U^{235} (n, f) Mo^{99}$ was evaluated by irradiating a known amount of uranium (1 mg) in the form of uranyl nitrate and 100 mg of the ore with thermal neutrons and separating radiochemically pure Mo^{99} by following the procedure outlined earlier. The activity of Mo^{99} was measured as described before.

Solvents and reagents used were of Analar grade.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analyses of copper ores examined are given in Table I. It is not possible to determine molybdenum in these ores by non-destructive neutron activation method because of serious interference caused by other activities produced during thermal neutron activation.

3. R. Pribil, *Collection Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1950, **15**, 120.

4. A. Smales, *Analyst*, 1952, **7**, 778.

5. E. B. Sandell, *Colorimetric determination of trace elements* (Interscience Publishers), 3rd ed., 1959.

TABLE I
Analysis of Copper Ores

Constituents	Bihar (%)	Gujarat (%)
Cu	15.39	17.46
Fe	33.55	5.6
Al	0.15	4.24
Ca	6.68	6.29
SiO ₂	16.70	33.96
Ni	0.65	—
S	24.29	—
Re and Mo	Trace	Trace
U	Trace	—

The results in Table II suggest that the purification steps described earlier give fairly good decontamination from elements studied, except Cr(III), Hg(III), Ru(III), Os(VI) and W(VI).

TABLE II
*Decontamination from different elements**

Yield of molybdenum ~ 50%

Isotope	Decontamination factor (Df)
Fe ⁵⁹ (III)	1.38 × 10 ⁵
Co ⁶⁰ (II)	1.07 × 10 ⁵
Cu ⁶⁴ (II)	9.03 × 10 ⁴
Re ¹⁸⁶ (VII)	9.78 × 10 ⁴
Sb ¹²⁴ (III)	3.6 × 10 ⁵
Ce ¹⁴¹ (III)	2.5 × 10 ⁵
Br ⁸² (I)	3.4 × 10 ⁵
Mn ⁵⁶ (II)	8.14 × 10 ⁴
Ir ¹⁹² (IV)	6.5 × 10 ⁴
Zr ⁹⁵ (IV)	3.18 × 10 ⁴
P ³² (V)	2.69 × 10 ⁴
Ag ¹¹⁰ (I)	2.6 × 10 ⁴
As ⁷⁶ (III)	2.4 × 10 ⁴
Zn ⁶⁵ (II)	2.24 × 10 ⁴
Cd ¹¹⁵ (II)	1.69 × 10 ⁴
Cs ¹³⁷ (I)	1.07 × 10 ⁴
Sn ¹¹³ (IV)	5.23 × 10 ³
Cr ⁵¹ (III)	4.2 × 10 ³
Hg ²⁰³ (II)	2.52 × 10 ³
Ru ¹⁰³ (III)	1.0 × 10 ³
Os ¹⁹¹ (VI)	5.89 × 10 ²
W ¹⁸⁷ (VI)	3

* Df = $\frac{\text{Activity taken}}{\text{Activity in the purified sample}}$

Decay curve (Figure 1) and aluminium absorption curve (Figure 2) of purified Mo sample indicate that it is radio-chemically pure. The gamma-ray spectrum of the sample shown in Figure 3 also confirms its purity. It may be concluded from the results in Table III that the proposed method permits to determine molybdenum in copper ores with an accuracy of 5% and a precision of 2.5%. The procedure for the purification of molybdenum takes less than 40 min. and chemical yield is around 50%. The sensitivity for molybdenum is 0.2 μg . calculated on the basis of production of 50 disintegrations per second at a thermal

Fig. 1

TABLE III

Determination of Molybdenum in Copper Ores

Amount irradiated = 0.1 g.

Duration of irradiation = 1 to 8 days.

Neutron flux = $1-2 \times 10^{12}$ n/cm²/sec.

Internal or external standard = 1-10 μg of molybdenum.

Material	Molybdenum (μg)		Ore from	Molybdenum Activation (at 95% confidence limits) $\mu\text{g/g}$.	Colori- metric* $\mu\text{g/g}$.
	Taken	Found			
Synthetic	20.0	19.0	Gujarat	$77.60 \pm 0.95^{**}$	76.0
Mixture	10.0	10.4	Bihar	$163.50 \pm 1.13^{***}$	161.6

* 0.25—1 g of the ore taken for analysis.

** Average of 5 determinations.

*** Average of 6 determinations.

neutron flux of 2×10^{12} n/cm²/sec, an irradiation period of one week, a chemical yield of 50% and counting of the sample after 4 days from the end of irradiation. The values for molybdenum with internal and external standards do not differ by more than 3% and so the self-shielding effect is negligible. The results of molybdenum estimation by activation method are in very good agreement with those of colorimetric method⁵ considering the errors involved in the measurements. Since the ore from Bihar is radioactive and contains uranium, it has been analysed for uranium by two independent methods^{4,5} and the results are shown in Table IV.

Fig. 2

TABLE IV

Determination of Uranium in Copper Ores

Method	Bihar ore taken (g)	Uranium ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
Activation*	0.1	85.7
Colorimetric	2.5	85.0

* 1 mg of uranium in the form of uranyl nitrate was used as a standard.

Fig. 3

Knowing the value (85.7 $\mu\text{g/g}$) for uranium in the ore and measuring the activity of Mo^{99} produced by irradiating a known weight of uranium, the contribution due to Mo^{99} from the reaction $\text{U}^{235} (n, \gamma) \text{Mo}^{99}$ has been evaluated and the corrected values for molybdenum are recorded in Table III.

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